

NATIONAL AND CULTURAL SPECIFICITY OF SPEECH ACTS OF A COMPLIMENT IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN

<https://doi.org/>

ELSEVIER

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Abstract: The French word "etiquette" means "label". This idea is regarded as a philosophical, ethical, and linguistic and cultural notion and therefore the failure of etiquette in speech is a great problem of communication. As everybody knows, etiquette, including speech, may be a set of rules of behavior that are associated with the external manifestation of attitudes to people. The external manifestation usually shows the inner essence of the connection, which should naturally be mutually polite and type. But the very fact that etiquette has a national character, has its own cultural characteristics, takes it beyond the scope of one science.

The study of speech etiquette needs special attention because it stands at the intersection of linguistics, cultural theory and history, ethnography, country studies, psychology, and other disciplines. Here, we will consider etiquette from the point of view of linguoecology as an obligatory component of linguoculturology. The article analyzes the national and cultural specificity of compliments in Russian and English.

Keywords: speech etiquette, specificity of compliments, information transfer, communicative situations, interlocutor, speech behavior, an equivalent phenomenon, an equal phenomenon.

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Received: 28-11-2022

Accepted: 01-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

INTRODUCTION

Language is a special world, and without this fertile land there would be no world culture. It has long been known that with the help of language, a person can perceive himself and establish a relationship with his environment. Humans are surrounded by language spaces all their lives. At the same time, language is not just a means of communication and information transfer. It also represents the environment in which a person is formed and exists. Man lives in language, is always in it, and experiences its influence. Language, as a means of communications, reflects the reality of social strata found in any linguistic society. Besides, the relationship between the interlocutors and their relative status can cause an adaptation of certain linguistic rules which are reflected on the use of considerable lexical and grammatical variations [8].

The most important function of the language is to preserve culture and pass it on to the future generations. It is in this connection that language plays a very significant, even decisive role in shaping the personality and character of a nation or people. The relationship between culture and language can be considered as the relationship of the whole and its part. Language can be perceived as a component of culture or an instrument of culture (which is not the same thing), especially when it

comes to a literary language or the language of folklore. However, language is at the same time Autonomous in relation to culture as a whole, and it can be considered separately from culture (which is constantly done) or in comparison with culture as an equivalent and equal phenomenon [7].

THE MAIN PART

The specificity of Russian and English culture, the characteristics and national nature of the representatives of the two linguistic and cultural communities determine the differences in consciousness and evaluative statements in Russian and English. At the same time, the national and cultural specificity of speech acts of compliment in Russian and English speech communication is manifested both in the content of statements and in their form. In this article, we will try to reveal the characteristic national and cultural features of a compliment using the example of fiction in Russian and English.

The dictionary of the modern Russian literary language gives the following interpretation: "A compliment is praise caused by the desire to say courtesy or flatter someone." Thus, the compliment here is synonymous with praise and flattery [4].

A compliment, as an evaluative statement, can highlight individual specific features of a person and the personality as a whole, abilities and virtues, and other features. The list of possible potential objects for a compliment is practically unlimited, but, both in Russian and English communicative culture and speech etiquette, there is a list of the most common objects for complimentary statements [3]. The results of R. Serebryakova's study of praise and compliments in Russian and English communication testify to the existing differences in the evaluative communicative consciousness of Russians and Englishmen. The results of the study are shown in Table 1. The data are presented as a percentage of each type of compliment from the total number of speech acts.

Analysis of the frequency of compliments in Russian and English communicative cultures depending on the object of compliments		
Types of compliments	Russian	English
Compliments about the appearance of a person	47%	21%
Compliments for assessing the professionalism or specific abilities of a person	19%	20%
Generalized compliments or characterization of the individual as a whole	16%	10%

Compliments on the internal and moral component of a person	9%	37%
Other compliments (for example, regarding the name, age, housing, etc.)	9%	12%

Based on the presented data, we can conclude that Russian national culture is most characterized by compliments in relation to the appearance of a person, while in English - compliments about the inner component of the personality and its moral qualities. As factors for the presence of these differences, it is probably worth noting the unequal hierarchy of the value system in the two linguistic cultures under consideration, as well as significant differences in the etiquette of the two analyzed cultures. The factual material based on the results of the analysis of literary texts by A. S. Pushkin "The Captain's Daughter" and "The Queen of Spades" in Russian, as well as Oscar Wilde "The Picture of Dorian Gray" and Arthur Golden "Memoirs of a Geisha" in English, indicates on the prevalence of the speech act of complimenting the appearance of a person. Here are examples from the analyzed texts:

-«*You have a wonderfully beautiful face, Mr. Gray. Don't frown*» [6]

-«*This one's rather pretty, isn't she? Such unusual eyes!*» [5]

-«*Oh, she is better than good – she is beautiful*» [6].

-«*She crouched on the floor like a wounded thing, and Dorian Gray, with his beautiful eyes, looked down at her, and his chiseled lips curled in exquisite disdain*» [6].

-«*Как же! очень было весело; танцевали до пяти часов. Как хороша была Елецкая!*» [2].

-«*Лизавета Ивановна была сто раз милее наглых и холодных невест, около которых они увивались*» [2].

-«*Один из них изображал мужчину лет сорока, румяного и полного, в светло-зеленом мундире и со звездой; другой – молодую красавицу с орлиным носом, с зачесанными висками и с розою в пудренных волосах*» [2].

-«*Тут вошла девушка лет осьмнадцати, круглолицая, румяная, с светло-русыми волосами, гладко зачесанными за уши, которые у ней так и горели. С первого взгляда она не очень мне понравилась*» [1].

-«*Сосед мой, молодой казак, стройный и красивый, налил мне стакан простого вина, до которого я не коснулся*» [1].

In the above quotes, complimentary statements not only characterize the appearance of a person as a whole, but also individual parts of the appearance, such as eyes, face, figure, etc. Such evaluative statements are equally common in Russian and English communicative culture. If we consider the category of

compliments to the inner qualities of a person, the most frequent type of evaluative statements in English communicative culture, then we can give the following examples from Russian and English sources:

-«*She seems like a nice girl*» [5].

-«*He has a simple and a beautiful nature*» [6].

-«*Probably she's just as you say. But she looks to me like a very clever girl, and adaptable*» [5].

-«*My uncle was a very nice man*» she said [5].

-«*Opposite was the Duchess of Harley, a lady of admirable good-nature and good temper, much liked by everyone who knew her, and of those ample architectural proportions that in women who are not duchesses are described by contemporary historians as stoutness*» [6].

-«*Он имел сильные страсти и огненное воображение, но твердость спасла его от обыкновенных заблуждений молодости*» [2].

-«*Мы тотчас познакомились. Швабрин был очень не глуп. Разговор его был остр и занимателен*». [1]

-«*Василиса Егоровна прехрабрая дама, – заметил важно Швабрин. – Иван Кузмич может это засвидетельствовать*» [1].

Compliments of the internal component of a person in Russian culture can be expressed in highlighting any features of a person that distinguish him from other people, and not in the form of a direct compliment, as the above examples demonstrate. From the typology of complimentary statements with national characteristics of Russian and English culture, we examined the most frequent categories using examples, and based on the analysis of the actual material, it becomes obvious that the speech acts of a compliment are based on a frame that includes images of the addresser (the subject of the compliment), the addressee or a third person absent in the communicative space, as well as the subject (object) of the compliment. In general, the list of objects of complimentary speech acts is quite diverse, but the studies carried out in this area make it possible to single out the object orientation of compliments that is most typical for Russian and English communicative cultures.

Conclusion

It is important to understand that the etiquette norms of speech also provide for certain rules for all participants in the speech act. The rules for the speaker include a friendly attitude to the interlocutor, appropriate politeness in this communication situation, modesty in selfassessment, selection of language tools in accordance with the chosen stylistic tone of the text, etc. In the rules for the listener, we find attentive listening, kindness, respect and patience towards the speaker, putting the speaker and his interests in the center of attention, timely reaction by action and verbally, etc. It can be concluded about the different manifestation of

evaluateness in the communicative consciousness of Russians and Englishmen and about the differences in the focus of complimenting in the two communicative cultures. Russians in communication mainly pay attention to external factors, which confirms the productivity in the Russian communicative culture of compliments to a person's appearance. For the British, internal factors play a big role, which is manifested in the frequent use of compliments on the moral qualities and intellectual abilities of a person.

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